

CRITICAL REVIEW: LANGUAGE EDUCATION AND SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION

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The article "A educação linguística crítica e metodologias ativas: promovendo experiências de aprendizagem na aula de Português" (Critical language education and active methodologies: promoting learning experiences in the Portuguese language classroom), by Malta, Silva, Emiliano, and Araújo, discusses how the combination of critical theories and dynamic practices can give a new face to language teaching. The authors get straight to the point, making it clear that if we remain stuck in the traditional model, we will not get anywhere. They argue that the use of technologies and strategies that move the student from the position of passive listener are fundamental to transforming the classroom into a multiliteracy environment, where the student truly feels part of the learning process.

In the text "Educação linguística crítica para a transformação social radical: discussões sobre letramentos, criticidade e afeto em tempos de barbárie" (Critical language education for radical social transformation: discussions on literacies, criticality, and affect in times of barbarism), Rogério Tilio and Claudia Hilsdorf Rocha bring a deeper and more human perspective. They emphasize that being critical is not enough if there is no affect. For the authors, language teaching needs to be aligned with a very clear political and ethical stance, especially in today's world, marked by so much intolerance. They reclaim the essence of Paulo Freire to remind us that educating, above all, is an act of building bridges through our humanity and respect for differences.

Looking at the two texts together, it becomes clear that the path is not to choose between method or theory, but rather to have one feed into the other.

The first article gives us the "how-to" — the tools, the dynamism of active methodologies. The second gives us the "why" — the ethical compass that ensures all this technology is not just used to check a box, but to truly form more conscious individuals. The key insight is that the act of teaching is never neutral;

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every time we enter the classroom, we are taking a political stance, and what defines the quality of that class is how much we can be both human and critical at the same time.

I recommend reading these texts to any colleague who feels that Portuguese Language teaching needs to move beyond the commonplace. They are not ready-made instruction manuals, but rather invitations for us to rethink our practice. In times when it seems that the school is bombarded by technical demands, being reminded that criticality and affect are the pillars of an education that truly changes lives is a relief and, at the same time, a necessary challenge for those who believe in the power of teaching.

For those who wish to delve deeper, it is worth getting to know the authors better: Daniela Malta and her team bring valuable contributions on technology and inclusion, while Rogério Tilio is one of the most respected voices in Brazil when it comes to critical teaching and the pedagogy of multiliteracies. Tilio, in particular, has several other works that deepen this vision that language education can be an engine of social change, and not just a mechanical teaching of grammatical rules. Both texts complement each other and give us the strength to face the challenges of our daily practice.

References

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